

TREASURE

DEMONSTRATING LARGE PIT THERMAL ENERGY STORAGES

Survey Highlights Key Trends and Challenges in Thermal Energy Storage

Findings from the TREASURE project survey will help guide large-scale heat storage implementation in cities.

A recent survey conducted by Hamburg Institut, as part of the TREASURE project, has gathered valuable insights from satellite projects across the TREASURE network. The goal was to support the development of a practical "**Implementation Guideline for Large-Scale Thermal Energy Storage (LTES) on City Level**," a key deliverable designed to assist municipalities, utilities, and decision-makers in planning and deploying **Pit Thermal Energy Storage (PTES)** systems in urban environments.

Conducted as part of **Task 3.7** of the TREASURE project, the survey gathered the latest knowledge and field experience from initiatives in **Denmark, France, Austria, and Croatia**, with an additional international reference project from **China**. Respondents shared their experiences in areas such as planning, approval procedures, site selection, and technical design.

Despite differences in national contexts, several common patterns emerged across all projects:

- **PTES systems** were consistently designed to store **seasonal surplus heat** and reduce peak heating demand during winter months.
- Every project included the use of **heat pumps** for post-heating.

However, the survey also revealed important differences and challenges that future projects will need to address:

- **Financing models varied widely**, from projects fully funded through private equity to those heavily reliant on public subsidies.
- **Delays** in permitting, planning, and tendering were reported as a significant barrier across most projects. These delays occurred even when authorities were considered technically experienced.

Our partners will synthesise these findings to support the Implementation Guideline for LTES on Large City Level, which will offer practical, experience-based recommendations for cities considering the integration of **PTES** into their **district heating systems**.

As European cities accelerate efforts to decarbonise heating systems and ensure energy security, **seasonal thermal energy storage** is emerging as a key technology. The forthcoming guideline will help local authorities and energy providers make informed decisions and overcome common implementation hurdles.

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